

*Under the Auspices of His Excellency Prof. Dr. Abdel Moneim El Banna,
Minister of Agriculture and Land Reclamation*

Arab Journal of Plant Protection

Volume 35, Special Issue, November 2017

Abstracts Book

12th Arab Congress of Plant Protection

Organized by
Arab Society for Plant Protection
&
Agricultural Research Center

Represented by
Plant Protection Research Institute & Plant Pathology Research Institute

Hurghada, Egypt
4-10 November 2017

Edited by

Safaa G. Kumari, Khaled Makkouk, Bassam Bayaa, Hassan Dahi,
Walaa Gamil and Mohsen M. Amin

ATGTCGATYCCWATYAAGTSTCAC-3', BC77 5'-TTAC ATAGTYGMWGCYACCCCAAAG-3', BC78 5'-TGCTCCAACAAAGAAATTC CC-3' and BC79 5'-TTCTGCCATCTGGAGTGAGGC-3', Ps62 5'-AAAGATGTTTTTCATG TTCTCT-3', Ps63 5'-TATTTAAAGCGAAACATGAT-3' and CPV-1 5'-GCTTCCTG GAAAAGCTGATG-3' and CPV-1 5'-GCTTCCTG GAAAAGCTGATG-3' were used to amplify of CPsV coat protein gene. The infected plants showed the expected size of CPsV coat protein fragments (350, 514, 600 bp) which was absent in the healthy plants. For biological indexing, 10 samples were inoculated on Pineapple orange seedlings to see the leaf symptoms of the virus. The first growth flushes of infected indicator trees showed vein banding and shock reaction of CPsV. Blast analysis showed that nucleotide sequences had greater than 98% nucleotide identity with corresponding region of CPsV reference genomes.

V17 APPLICATION OF HIGH-THROUGHPUT SEQUENCING APPROACH TO DEFINE THE SANITARY STATUS OF CERTIFIED AUTOCHTHONOUS GRAPEVINE CULTIVARS.

Michela Chiumenti¹, Massimiliano Morelli¹, Raied Abou Kubaa¹, Vito Nicola Savino², Pierfederico La Notte¹, Angelantonio Minafra¹ and Pasquale Saldarelli¹. (1) Istituto di Virologia Vegetale del CNR, UOS Bari, Via Amendola 165/A, 70126, Bari, Italy, Email: raied.aboukubaa@ipsp.cnr.it; (2) Dipartimento di Scienze del Suolo, della Pianta e degli Alimenti (Di. S. S. P. A.), Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro, 70126 Bari, Italy.

In Italy, grapevine certification system requires the status of "virus controlled" for multiplication and commercialization. This system entails free plant propagation material from *Grapevine virus A* (GVA), *Grapevine virus B* (GVB), *Grapevine leafroll-associated virus 1, 2, 3* (GLRaV-1, -2, -3), *Grapevine fanleaf virus* (GFLV), *Grapevine fleck virus* (GFkV) and *Arabis mosaic virus* (ArMV)]. Routinely applied bio- and molecular assays for the detection of systemic plant pathogens, such as wood indexing, serological and (RT-) PCR molecular tests, are time-consuming and always require *a priori* knowledge of the target. On the other hand, the availability of High-Throughput Sequencing (HTS) techniques, which are free from the abovementioned constraints, allows the characterization of the "virome" of the analysed plants. Indeed, data originating from HTS give an unbiased picture of the virus/viroid content of a plant. In this frame, a task of the Apulian Regional Project Re. Ge. Vi. P (Recovery of Apulian grape germplasm) aims to assess the sanitary status of 20 certified autochthonous grapevine clones, table and wine cultivars, by HTS. In 2016, small RNAs (sRNAs) libraries were synthesized from 20 grape accessions and subjected to Illumina sequencing. The downstream data were processed using a custom-developed bioinformatics pipeline including the quality control of the libraries, the *de novo* assembly of the reads using Velvet assembler and the Blast annotation of the obtained contigs. Annotated contigs confirmed the absence of the above-regulated viruses. Also, this approach showed the presence of two viruses and two

viroids not targeted in routinely performed assays, i. e. Grapevine rupestris stem pitting-associated virus (GRSPaV), Grapevine rupestris vein feathering virus (GRVfV), Hop stunt viroid (HSVd) and Grapevine yellow speckle viroid 1 (GYSVd-1). These results, confirmed by RT-PCR assays, strengthen the potentiality of HTS approach in plant "virome" definition and its application in grapevine certification schemes.

NEMATODES

N1
DISTRIBUTION AND IDENTIFICATION OF POTATO CYST NEMATODES FROM AIN DEFLA REGION, ALGERIA. N. Tirchi¹, A. Mokabli¹, A. Troccoli², F. De Luca² and E. Fanelli². (1) University Djilali Bounaama of Khemis Miliana, Ain Defla, Algeria, Email: tirchin1977@yahoo.fr; mokaissa@yahoo.fr; (2) Istituto per la Protezione Sostenibile delle Piante-CNR di Bari, Italy, Email: francesca.deluca@ipsp.cnr.it; a.troccoli@ba.ipp.cnr.it; elena.fanelli@ipsp.cnr.it

Potato cyst nematodes (PCNs) are the most economically damaging pests of potato crop worldwide. During 2013, a survey was carried out in Ain Defla region of Algeria. 81 soil samples collected from potato fields of 14 locations were submitted to nematological analysis which indicated the presence of these nematodes in 22.22% of the surveyed fields. Sixteen PCN populations from five locations were characterized by combination of features the perineal regions of cysts and those of second stage juveniles. The morphological identification has been confirmed by the analysis of the ITS-RFLP profiles, sequencing and phylogenetic analysis of the ITS region. The results revealed that the two species *Globodera rostochiensis* and *G. pallida* were present in this region, occurring separately or in mixed populations. However, dominance of *G. pallida* was noted, since only 12.25% of the populations were identified such as *G. rostochiensis*, whereas 31.5% were *G. pallida* and 56.25% of the populations consisted of a mixture of the two species, and among these mixed populations, 77.77% showed a dominance of *G. pallida*. The predominance of *G. pallida* has been noted in the sites of Ain Defla, El Amra, Mekhatria and Arib. *G. rostochiensis* was dominant in Rouina. Intraspecific variation was noted between populations of *G. rostochiensis* and *G. pallida*. Because of the high divergence among Algerian populations of *G. pallida* and *G. rostochiensis*, it can be assumed that they were multi-introduced in Algeria. The most divergent population of *G. pallida*, that formed a well separated group with some populations from Chile and Peru, suggests a later or independent introduction of this population in Algeria.

N2
IN VITRO NEMATICIDAL ACTIVITIES OF SOME MEDICINAL PLANT EXTRACTS ON EGGS AND SECOND-STAGE JUVENILES OF ROOT-KNOT NEMATODE (*MELOIDOGYNE INCOGNITA*) IN MALETE, KWARA STATE, NIGERIA. O.S. Osunlola and T.H. Gbadeyan, Department of Crop Production,